

RELIGIOUS IDENTITY AND PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT IN ADOLESCENCE

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Adolescence is one of the stages of development that plays an important role in the formation of human personality. During this period, individuals not only assimilate social roles and values, but also try to determine their own moral and worldview position, their own social and spiritual identities. Religious identity, as one of these forms of identity, also affects the formation of an individual's value system and worldview. The aim of the article is to analyze the socio-psychological essence of religious identity in adolescence, the theoretical content of the concept of religious identity, the mechanisms of its formation and the role of the personality in self-consciousness on the basis of scientific literature. The study was carried out using the qualitative analysis method based not on the collection of empirical data, but on the systematic study of existing psychological and sociological literature. The article considers religious identity as a complex socio-psychological phenomenon related to the individual's religious beliefs, moral values and sense of religious belonging. The theoretical analysis shows that religious identity can play an important role in the development of adolescents' self-awareness, the formation of a value system and the understanding of the meaning of life. As a result, religious identity acts as one of the important components of the personality structure during adolescence and can be considered one of the important factors affecting the spiritual and psychological development of the individual.

Keywords: Adolescence, religious identity, personality development, social environment, spiritual values.

INTRODUCTION. Relevance of the topic. In modern psychological research, adolescence is considered one of the most important stages of personality formation. During this period, the individual goes through the process of self-awareness, determining his position in the system of social relations and forming various identity components. Psychological and social changes occurring during adolescence have a significant impact on the formation of an individual's value system, worldview and behavioral directions.

In modern society, socio-cultural transformations, globalization processes and the interaction of various value systems are giving new directions to the identity formation of adolescents. In this context, religious identity attracts attention as one of the socio-psychological components that play an important role in the process of individual self-identification. Religious identity is a complex form of identity that reflects not only the adoption of religious beliefs, but also the individual's attitude to spiritual values, the process of making sense of life, and social behavior models.

In this regard, the study of the characteristics of the formation of religious identity in adolescence and its interaction with personality development is one of the current scientific problems for modern psychological research.

Scientific and practical significance of the topic. The study of the relationship of religious identity with the personality development of adolescents is important both theoretically and practically. From a theoretical point of view, this study can contribute to a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of formation of religious identity in adolescence within the framework of identity theories and developmental psychology.

From a practical point of view, the study of the impact of religious identity on the psychological development of adolescents can provide an opportunity to obtain important results that can be applied in educational institutions, in psychological and social work with young people, as well as in the upbringing process.

Problem statement and research gap. In modern scientific literature, the topic of religious identity has been studied from various aspects. The impact of religious identity on an individual's social behavior, moral values, and life position has been widely discussed in studies. However, most of the existing studies have used quantitative methods in studying religious identity.

As a result, in-depth research on adolescents' personal experiences with religious identity, how they perceive religious beliefs, and what meaning these beliefs give to personality formation has remained somewhat limited. Studying adolescents' subjective experiences and meaning-making processes regarding religious identity necessitates the application of qualitative research methods.

In this regard, investigating the characteristics of religious identity formation during adolescence in the context of individuals' personal experiences is of particular importance in terms of eliminating the existing research gap.

Purpose of the study. The main purpose of the study is to investigate the characteristics of religious identity formation during adolescence and its relationship with personality development based on the qualitative analysis method.

Scientific novelty of the study. Unlike existing studies, this study does not only measure religious identity, but also examines adolescents' subjective experiences with religious identity and their The meanings

they give to religious identity are analyzed. Within the framework of the study, the individual experiences of adolescents regarding their religious identity and the role this identity plays in their personality development process were determined. At the same time, the interaction of religious identity with social and psychological factors in the process of adolescents' self-identification was systematized on the basis of qualitative analysis.

Research questions. In accordance with the purpose of the study, the following research questions were put forward:

How do adolescents perceive religious identity and how do they perceive it as part of their identity?

In what way do religious values affect the process of adolescent personality development?

The concept of identity is considered a person's ability to understand himself. The concept of identity is expressed in English as "identity", and in Latin as "identitas". According to I. Zargan in his work "Man, Identity and Identification", the concept of identity expresses the self-awareness of the individual, self-perception, the ability to adapt to social society, and the assessment of one's own potential (Zargan, n.d). Identity is a unique, different, and unrepeatable state of balance that stands out from the crowd (Bayramov & Alizadeh, 2009).

Based on the approaches and relevant ideas of representatives of modern psychology on the study of identity, these approaches look at the issue of studying personality from different perspectives. These theoretical approaches complement each other and do not contradict each other, take into account different aspects of the identity phenomenon and create an opportunity to better study personality. Social identity is related to both personal identity and social processes (Waterman, 1985).

The concept of religious identity is accepted in modern psychology as one of the structural elements of personality and plays an important role in the individual's self-awareness, the formation of his worldview, the system of social relations and behavioral strategies. Religious identity is valued not only as a set of beliefs, but also as a key component of a person's understanding of himself and the world, and determining his goals and directions in life.

In psychological approaches, religious beliefs are presented as an important mechanism in regulating human behavior and forming a spiritual and moral system. From this perspective, religious identity is formed in an environment of interaction between internal and external factors that affect the development of an individual's personality and acts as a stable and enduring component in the structure of the personality. Studies show that religious values and beliefs determine the meaning an individual gives to life events, the ability to self-regulate in difficult situations, and psychological resilience. Thus, religious identity is not only a part of the spiritual system, but also a psychological mechanism that plays an important role in the social and emotional adaptation of the personality (Jensen, 2021).

Religious identity is also crucial in establishing an individual's relationships with the social environment

and integrating them into the cultural values of society. It shapes how a person perceives himself in a social context and how he behaves based on this perception. This process strengthens self-awareness and self-concept at the individual level, and determines the structure of mutual relations and social participation at the social level (Nechyporenko et al., 2019).

Religious identity, as one of the main structural components of an individual's self-system, plays an important role in the formation of his worldview, self-awareness and psychological health. In addition to providing a person with deep ideas about the meaning of life, it acts as a source of social support and moral support, and at the same time strengthens the fight against stress and emotional resilience (Ayub et al., 2022).

Leicht et al. (2021) showed that the content of religious doctrines directly shapes attitudes towards science and technology. More stringent religious rules result in a cautious and critical approach to scientific innovations (Leicht et al., 2021). These ideas are also consistent with the study of Alkhouri (2024); he analyzed the impact of artificial intelligence on religious identity and emphasized that technological changes are reshaping people's understanding of faith (Alkhouri, 2024).

According to Schmees and colleagues (2024), religious discrimination manifests itself in various forms and the social exclusion of religious minorities negatively affects emotional and physical health (Schmees et al., 2024). These results are also confirmed by the study of Veerasamy et al. (2023): religious experiences reduce stress, enhance emotional well-being and increase life satisfaction. However, the attitude towards religion in psychology is still not unanimous (Veerasamy et al., 2023). Sharkey (2022) emphasized that religious identity affects human self-determination at both the internal (beliefs) and external (social environment) levels. All these studies highlight the multifaceted nature of religious identity and the ten Religion plays a major role in shaping adolescent behavior. Given the importance of religion, researchers have examined how religious identity develops. Religious identity is the meaning people give to their religious group membership, which in turn influences their sense of belonging (Arweck & Nesbitt, 2010).

Religious affiliation is influenced by factors such as generational status, ethnicity, and gender (King & Boyatzis, 2004). Religious identity is shaped by the devotional, social, psychological, and political aspects of religious affiliation (Deaux, 2001).

Religious identity is a set of affiliations, beliefs, and experiences that are determined by various factors. Research has shown that the most important part of religious identity is the belief system. The essence of religious identity is belief, which, if well-embedded, leads to appropriate religious behavior and religious commitment (Copen & Silverstein, 2008).

Parents are an important determinant of religious identity. Parents have a great influence on individuals' religious ideologies (Yi et al., 2004). Parents have left lasting marks on their children's religious commitments

and ideologies (Bengtson, 2001). Parents have an important role in children's participation in religious activities and the formation of faith identity. For parents, transmitting their beliefs to their children is part of their parental responsibilities (Horwath et al., 2008).

Religious identity is one of the most relevant research areas in modern psychology and social sciences. This concept expresses a person's conscious understanding of his or her relationship with spiritual values, religious beliefs, and the religious community to which he or she belongs. Adolescence is considered the most sensitive and dynamic stage for the formation of this identity. At this stage, a young individual begins a search to find his or her "self", understand the meaning of life, and determine a value system. Religious identity emerges as part of these psychosocial searches and plays an important role in the integration of the adolescent's personality. According to Erik Erikson's (1968) theory of psychosocial development, identity formation is a lifelong process, but its main stage occurs during adolescence. Erikson considers religious identity as a component of the overall "self" structure and notes that religious affiliation gives the adolescent both moral stability and social orientation. In his opinion, the assimilation of values and the establishment of a belief system are key factors in the integration of personality (Erikson, 1968).

Fowler (1981) has shown that religious belief and identity develop in stages. The adolescence stage is the main stage when a person consciously realizes his religious identity (Fowler, 1981).

Modern psychological and sociological research shows that religious identity plays an important role in the spiritual development of adolescents, the formation of social relationships, and the determination of life goals. Smith and Denton's (2005) study "Soul Searching" shows that parents' religious practices and beliefs directly determine adolescents' religious orientation. The family model plays the role of both moral guidance and behavioral role model. At the same time, in modern times, social media, cultural globalization, and ideas of individual freedom create flexible and multi-level forms of religious identity in young people (Smith & Denton, 2005).

Adolescence is considered one of the most important developmental stages in human life. This stage is characterized by the growth of the individual, self-awareness, and the formation of his or her identity. The messages that adolescents receive from the cultural environment they belong to—through the media, peer groups, and other social influences—create an idea of what behaviors they should exhibit and what ideals they should strive for, and this significantly affects the formation of personality, as well as psychological well-being (Stryker & Burke, 2000).

After the childhood stage ends, a completely new stage of development begins in human life, which is different from previous periods, and this stage is called adolescence (Bayramov & Alizadeh, 2003). According to psychologists, over time, due to the diversity of the period, adolescents develop extreme and instinctive tendencies, special mental and psychological feelings, which intensify their direction towards religious and

moral issues. Family, friends, school, social environment and other related factors can create spiritual evolution and mature ideas in adolescents, as well as lead them to the right path. Thus, over time and over the next many years, that person will make changes in their religious, spiritual and social identity and personality, their behaviors such as evil, suffering, greed, suffering, stress, theft and lying will decrease and be eliminated, and the adolescent will be directed towards the path of religion and human morality (Bayramov, 1981).

Adolescence is characterized in psychology as a transitional or "crisis" stage, which is not accidental. Factors such as psychophysiological renewals, changes in the system of relationships, and differences in the perspective of oneself and others that occur at this stage reshape the behavior and attitude of the teenager, have a strong impact on the perception of new potential opportunities and individual characteristics in his "I" concept. These factors create conditions for determining the teenager's identity, directing his ideas and desires in a specific direction. In such conditions, fundamental questions such as "Who am I?", "What will my life path be like?", "Where will my future lead me?" arise in the teenager's mind, which also prompt him to think deeply and search for answers. At this age, young people carefully analyze problems, make decisions after weighing them, and do not easily compromise their adherence to their religious beliefs. If they observe a difference of opinion or practical inconsistency in the matter of religion, they react in two ways: if their faith is weak, this situation undermines their faith, otherwise they raise their voices of protest and demand that the principles of the religion be followed in all matters (Aliyev & Jabbarov, n.d.).

Religious identity is one of the most relevant research directions in modern psychology and social sciences. This concept expresses a conscious understanding of a person's relationship with spiritual values, religious beliefs and the religious community to which he belongs. Adolescence is considered the most sensitive and dynamic stage for the formation of this identity. At this stage, a young individual enters into a search for his "self", understanding the meaning of life and defining a system of values. Religious identity emerges as part of these psychosocial searches and plays an important role in the integration of the adolescent's personality (Erikson, 1968).

Methodology. In this study, a qualitative research approach was applied to investigate the issue of religious identity and personality development during adolescence. The methodological basis of the study is the analysis and comparison of various scientific approaches explaining the psychological and social aspects of religious identity. In the research process, the main focus was on the systematic study and analytical analysis of the existing scientific literature on the topic.

Research design. The design of the study is based on the analytical study of scientific sources on the topic. The main goal of the study was to systematize the theoretical approaches put forward by various researchers on religious identity and personality development during adolescence and to summarize their main content. This approach allows for a clearer understanding of the

psychological, social and cultural factors that affect the formation of religious identity. Within the framework of the study, both classical and modern scientific studies conducted on identity, religious identity and the psychological characteristics of adolescence were reviewed. In this context, Erik Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, Fowler's model of the stages of development of religious belief, as well as modern psychological approaches based on the theory of social identity formed the methodological basis of the study.

Data sources and selection principle. The main database of the study consists of scientific articles, monographs and studies published in international scientific journals published in different years. Several main criteria were taken into account when selecting the literature: the sources should be directly related to the topic of religious identity and personality development during adolescence; have scientific reliability and be published in academic publications; take into account modern research in addition to classical theoretical approaches. Based on these criteria, the works of Erikson, Fowler, Smith and Denton, Jensen, Veerasamy, Schmees and other researchers were selected as research material. These sources were analyzed in terms of the psychological content of religious identity, its interaction with the social environment and its impact on the personality development of adolescents.

Analysis procedure. The scientific sources selected within the framework of the study were analyzed using the qualitative content analysis method. The analysis process consists of several stages. In the first stage, the main theoretical approaches to the topic were identified and scientific ideas about religious identity, social identity and the characteristics of adolescence were reviewed in a general way. In the next stage, the data obtained were grouped in terms of content. This includes issues such as the concept of identity and social identity, the psychological structure of religious identity, its interaction with the social environment, identity formation during adolescence, as well as the influence of family, school and social environment on this process. Then, the ideas put forward by various researchers are analyzed comparatively and their similarities and differences are identified. Different aspects were identified. At the last stage, the results obtained were interpreted within the framework of psychological theories and the role of religious identity in the personality development of adolescents was summarized. The analyses conducted showed that religious identity is not limited only to the individual belief system, but is also a complex psychological process formed as a result of the interaction of family environment, social relations, cultural values, and personal life experiences.

Reliability and scientific substantiation of the study. In order to ensure the reliability of the study, the results of studies conducted in different countries and in different socio-cultural environments were reviewed and analyzed comparatively. This approach allowed us to more clearly identify both the general and contextual features of the process of religious identity formation.

In addition, the analysis of classical psychological theories together with the results of modern empirical studies created conditions for a more systematic study

of the topic. As a result, the phenomenon of religious identity was evaluated not only as a theoretical concept, but also as one of the important factors affecting the social and psychological development of adolescents.

Conclusion. As a result of the qualitative analysis, it was determined that religious identity acts as one of the main psychological and social factors affecting the formation of personality during adolescence. As a result of a comparative study of various scientific sources on the subject, it became clear that religious identity should be considered not only as a concept expressing an individual's religious beliefs, but also as a complex psychological phenomenon related to his self-concept, value system and social relations.

Theoretical studies conducted within the framework of the study showed that the concept of identity has a broad and multifaceted meaning in psychology. In the approaches of various researchers, identity is associated with a person's self-awareness, determining his position in the social environment and assessing his individual capabilities. In this regard, it was determined that religious identity is considered one of the important elements of the general identity structure and is formed in close connection with a person's life goals, values and behavioral motives.

The results of the study show that adolescence is a particularly sensitive stage in terms of the formation of religious identity. It was determined that during this period the individual tries to understand himself more deeply, thinks about the meaning of life and begins to form a personal value system. According to Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, the most active stage of identity formation occurs precisely at this age. Therefore, religious beliefs and moral values can play an important role in determining the direction of a teenager's life.

As a result of the analysis of theoretical sources, it was determined that the development of religious identity is not limited only to individual choice, but is also closely related to the influence of the social environment. In particular, the family environment and the religious values of parents play an important role in this process.

As a result of the analysis, it was determined that during adolescence, an individual encounters various social influences and that these influences affect his attitude to religious values to a certain extent. In modern times, the widespread use of information technologies and social media is considered one of the factors that additionally affects the formation of religious identity in young people, and it was determined that these factors can lead to the formation of religious identity in a more flexible and multi-level manner.

Studies also show that religious identity is also to a certain extent related to the psychological well-being of adolescents. Religious beliefs in many cases play the role of spiritual support for a person, help maintain emotional stability in difficult life situations and strengthen the ability to cope with stress. In this regard, it has been determined that religious identity is evaluated not only as a system of spiritual values, but also as one of the factors supporting the social adaptation and psychological stability of adolescents.

Thus, the theoretical analysis conducted shows that religious identity is one of the important factors influencing the formation of personality during adolescence. Research conducted in this area allows for a deeper understanding of the psychological development, social behavior and value system of adolescents. At the same time, the results obtained in this direction can also be used as an important scientific basis for the development of social and pedagogical programs supporting the spiritual and psychological development of adolescents in the future.

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